

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

THE PROBLEM OF HUMAN SELF-IMPROVEMENT IN GOETHE'S TRAGEDY "FAUST"

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Abstract

The authors of this article refer to Goethe's tragedy "Faust" due to the current problems of Russian education, which is influenced by digital didactics. The result of this influence, according to the authors, is a decrease in interest in self-knowledge as the basis of human self-improvement. The teacher's task is to arouse students' interest in learning themselves and investigating their future. Goethe's Faust presents a solution to this problem. A person (student) must objectively assess the level of his intellectual and spiritual development, in fact, test his abilities. Both a person's mind and feelings are put to the test. A person's faith in God is also being tested. The uncertainty of the meaning of the word *God* (both as a concept and as an idea), which Faust and Margarita discuss, speaks to the uncertainty of human knowledge. The negative experience of Faust's life, who trusted Mephistopheles, speaks about the need for independence in human life. Faust strives for freedom, but underestimates the presence of a natural human trait – dependence, which appears to him in the form of Care. At the end of his life, Faust understands the meaning of human life and expresses it in the words: "Nur der verdient sich Freiheit wie das Leben, Der täglich sie erobern muß" [1]. For modern readers of the tragedy "Faust," knowledge of Faust's life experience serves as the basis for determining the path and ways to achieve their meaning in life.

Keywords: life, meaning of life, knowledge, reason, feeling

Addressing the problem of human self-improvement is especially important for a teacher. The change of the modern world, its values, and the way a person interacts with it affects most of all the formation of a new generation of young people. The teacher is faced with the task of finding new means and ways of interacting with students. The solution of these tasks depends on the activities of both the teacher and the student, on the ability of each of them to self-improvement and self-development - one of the most important resources of human education. It is no accident that we understand education as the process of a person gaining conscious independence in mastering the space and time of his life. But a person should have a desire to improve himself, to improve his life. The absence of it means the loss of the meaning of life, its end.

«Werd' ich beruhigt je mich auf ein Faulbett legen,

So sey es gleich um mich gethan!» [1].

But man, as the Lord says, is weak by nature:

«Des Menschen Thätigkeit kann allzu leicht erschlaffen,

Er liebt sich bald die unbedingte Ruh...» [1].

Peace is a natural inclination of a person, and the acquired one is associated with his conscious activity, with human activity. And to awaken this activity, the Lord makes Faust's companion a demon, who teases him and stirs him up to action.

Human education is also a matter of concern. And the task of the teacher is to awaken in the student an interest in learning not only about the outside world, but

also about himself. Self-knowledge serves as the basis for self-improvement. It is with the characterization of Faust's self-knowledge that our acquaintance with him begins:

"Habe nun, ach! Philosophie,
Juristerey und Medicin,
Und leider auch Theologie!
Durchaus studirt, mit heißem Bemühn.
Da steh' ich nun, ich armer Thor!
Und bin so klug als wie zuvor...» [1].

Faust also negatively evaluates himself as a teacher:

"Die Menschen zu bessern und zu bekehren.
Auch hab' ich weder Gut noch Geld...» [1].

And this self-assessment of Faust leads him to study magic as another way of knowing the world:

"Drum hab' ich mich der Magie ergeben,
Ob mir durch Geistes Kraft und Mund...» [1].

However, the new method of cognition by itself does not guarantee knowledge of the mysteries of nature and man. I need to test my abilities. That is why Faust says:

"Ich ehle Muth, mich in die Welt zu wagen,
Der Erde Weh, der Erde Glück zu tragen,
Mit Stürmen mich herumzuschlagen,
Und in des Schiffbruchs Knirschen nicht zu zagen...» [1].

And then Faust says that the time has come to prove by deeds that human dignity is not inferior to the greatness of the gods:

«Hier ist es Zeit durch Thaten zu beweisen,

Daß Mannes-Würde nicht der Götterhöhe weicht...» [1].

Proof by deed is the right way to self-knowledge, to test a person's readiness for independent living, but the price of such self-knowledge is human life. And on this path, new challenges await a person, which not everyone can withstand. One of the universal tests is faith in God. And Faust, answering Margarita's question "Don't you believe?" [2], says:

«Nenn' es dann wie du willst,
Nenn's Glück! Herz! Liebe! Gott!
Ich habe keinen Nahmen Dafür! Gefühl ist alles;
Name ist Schall und Rauch,
Umnebelnd Himmelsgluth»
In response, Margarita exclaims:

"Das ist alles recht schön und gut..." [1].

Awareness of uncertainty turns out to be a boon for Margarita. The uncertainty of the meaning of words denoting the idea of love, beauty, soul and other similar words is inherent in human knowledge today. But do we perceive this kind of uncertainty as a blessing today? And what is the measure of the ratio of certainty and uncertainty in human cognition and human education today? The search for answers to these questions is one of the foundations of a person's self-knowledge and self-improvement.

The result of self-knowledge is a person's assessment of his actions. And Faust condemns himself for his attitude towards Margarita. The ordeal of mental anguish and suffering falls to the lot of Faust and Margarita. And Margarita prefers death to a shameful life. Faust and Mephistopheles leave her world. Faust acquired such a negative life experience in collaboration with Mephistopheles. And the reason for this result was Faust's loss of the independence of his actions, his appeal to magic. In his life path, a person encounters Vice, Sin, Care and Need. And Goethe gives them all a negative image of "ill-fated visions" [2] as Faust puts it. After meeting them, Faust realizes his dependence on them:

"Noch hab' ich mich in's Freie nicht gekämpft.
Könnst' ich Magie von meinem Pfad entfernen,
Die Zaubersprüche ganz und gar verlernen,
Stünd' ich, Natur! vor dir ein Mann allein,
Da wär's der Mühe werth ein Mensch zu seyn»

[1].

Left alone with Care, Faust defends his right to be free:

"Doch deine Macht, o Sorge, schleichend groß,
Ich werde sie nicht anerkennen» [1].

However, taking care of yourself and your loved ones is a natural human trait. With our soul, we worry about the lives of other people, for their better future. Faust says the same thing, summing up his life:

"Ja! diesem Sinne bin ich ganz ergeben,
Das ist der Weisheit letzter Schluß:
Nur der verdient sich Freiheit wie das Leben,
Der täglich sie erobern muß» [1].

With this statement Faust defines the meaning of human life. Summing up our acquaintance with Faust's life, we ask ourselves about the origins of his activity, about his desire for a full-fledged life, the life of the human mind and feelings. And we assign the defining role in Faust's life to the life of his feelings. Perhaps our conclusion was influenced by the form of the work – a tragedy, the content of which is a test of a person, his ability to live a decent life. Perhaps S. Turaev, a Soviet researcher of Goethe's work, is right speaking about the role of feelings in the work of writers of the Enlightenment: "... For European writers of the second half of the XVIII century, feeling was the banner of the struggle against cruelty, callousness, and soullessness that prevailed in feudal society. It was a struggle for man, for his multifaceted development" [2, p. 10]. Today, we are concerned about the importance of the role of feelings in the education of a person in the 21st century, about achieving harmony in the interaction of his feelings and mind. And Faust's life path, his critical attitude to his achievements, the search for ways of his development, and the meaning of life serve as the basis for solving the problems of modern human education.

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